

BLOCK COPOLYMERS ORGANIZATION AT INTERFACE

D.Fischer, S. Bistac^{*}, M. Brogly,
 Université de Haute Alsace, LPIM, Mulhouse France
^{*} Corresponding author (sophie.bistac-brogly@uha.fr)

Keywords: *block copolymer, crystallinity, interface, FTIR, AFM*

1 Introduction

Block copolymers are usually used as compatibilizer for thermoplastic polymers blends or as surfactant for the dispersion of filler in a polymer matrix. However, the organization and conformation of a block polymer can be different at an interface compared to its bulk chains organization, especially if the blocks are able to crystallize.

The objective of this work is focused on the effect of interface on the organization and crystallization of diblocks copolymers in thin films.

Polyethylene-b-Polyethylene glycol (PE-b-PEG) diblocks copolymers have been studied in thin films spin coated on aluminum substrates.

Polarization-Modulation Infrared Reflection Absorption Spectroscopy (PM-IRRAS), used to characterize PE-b-PEG thin films, allowed us to get information about the organization of both blocks. These results will be compared with bulk IR analysis performed by Attenuated Total Reflection Infrared Spectroscopy (ATR) in order to evidence specific chains organization in thin films and to reveal the interest of the PM-IRRAS method in the comprehension of copolymers adsorption mechanisms [1-3].

Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) analyses were also performed on thin polymer films, in order to characterize the surface morphology.

Various PE-b-PEG copolymers (different compositions and chains lengths) have been investigated in this study to better understand the chains organization at interface. The investigation of the role of the substrate surface chemistry on polymer chains organization would allow us to better understand what can happen at a fiber/polymer interface in composite materials.

2 Materials and Techniques

2.1 Materials

Different PE-b-PEG copolymers (with M_w varying from 575 g.mol⁻¹ to 2250g.mol⁻¹) and PEG homopolymer ($M_w = 2050$ g/mol) purchased from Sigma Aldrich were used.

They were characterized by size exclusion chromatography (SEC) and proton nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (¹H NMR) in order to quantify their composition and molecular weight.

These copolymers have been studied by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) in order to investigate the bulk crystalline properties: melting temperature and crystallinity degree (X_c).

The polymer characteristics are given in Table 1.

	M_w	PE block	PEG block
	[g/mol]	wt %	wt %
Cop1	2250	17	83
Cop2	575	78	22
PEG1	2050	-	100

Table 1: Characteristics of PE-b-PEG copolymers (Cop 1 and Cop 2) and PEG homopolymer (PEG 1)

Tetrahydrofuran (THF) was used for the preparation of polymer solutions (1 to 5g/l).

Thin films of copolymers and PEG were spin coated from solutions, with a velocity of 1000 rpm during 30 seconds on cleaned aluminum substrates and dried.

2.2 Techniques

Bulk copolymers and homopolymers (PEG and PE) were analyzed by single-reflection attenuated total reflection (ATR) spectroscopy with a Vertex 70 Bruker spectrometer. The number of scans was fixed to 50 scans with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} .

Thin films of copolymers PE-b-PEG deposited on aluminum substrates were characterized by Polarization-Modulation Infrared Reflection-Absorption Spectroscopy (PM-IRRAS). This technique consists in detecting the reflected infrared beam on a surface after its polarization and double modulation. The difference in reflectivity between both components of polarization (S and P) is characteristic of the layers adsorption on the surface. Due to the double modulation and the mathematical treatment of signals, the sensitivity of measurements is improved and noise of signals is reduced.

PM-IRRAS measurements were done with a Vertex 70 Bruker spectrometer in combination with a PMA 50 instrument developed for polarization-modulation IR spectroscopy. Experimental conditions were set to 1000 scans, resolution of 4 cm^{-1} and 80° beam incidence angle.

The AFM is a Bruker Dimension Edge driven by the software NanoDrive v8.01. The tip was supplied by Veeco, the model is TAP150 and is a Phosphorous (n) doped Si tip. Its stiffness constant is equal to 5 N.m^{-1} and its resonance frequency is near 154 kHz. The target tapping signal is 4 V and a 20x gain is used to obtain a clear image.

3 Results and discussion

Both PE and PEG blocks are able to crystallize (PEG and PE homopolymers are indeed semi-crystalline). DSC measurements were performed to analyze the crystallinity of each block of the copolymers. PEG is also analyzed. For all DSC curves, the bottom curve corresponds to the heating

step (second passage) and the top curve corresponds to the cooling step.

DSC curves of PEG homopolymer (PEG 1) is presented in figure 1.

Fig. 1 : DSC curves of PEG 1 ($M_w = 2050\text{ g/mol}$)

An endothermic peak corresponding to the melting of the PEG crystals can be observed. The melting enthalpy (ΔH , J/g) allows us to calculate the crystallinity degree (χ) of the polymer, which is equal to the ratio of the measured enthalpy on the melting enthalpy of a 100% crystalline polymer, which is equal to 205 J/g . For PE-b-PEG block copolymers, the crystallinity of PEG was calculated by taking into account the weight percentage of PEG in the copolymer.

For the PE blocks of PE-b-PEG copolymers, the crystallinity degree (χ) is equal to the ratio of the measured enthalpy on the melting enthalpy of a 100% crystalline PE, which is equal to 286 J/g . The crystallinity degree of PE was calculated by taking into account the weight percentage of PE in the copolymer.

Due to the fact that both PE and PEG blocks are able to crystallize, it would be interesting to investigate the crystallinity of each block in both diblocks copolymers.

Figures 2 and 3 show the DSC curves of PE-b-PEG copolymers, respectively 1 and 2.

Fig. 2. DSC curves of PE-b-PEG (Cop 1)

An intense melting peak can be observed on figure 2 at a temperature closed to the melting temperature of PEG homopolymer.

Fig. 3. DSC curves of PE-b-PEG (Cop 2)

A broad melting peak can be observed on figure 3 at a temperature nearest to the melting temperature of PE homopolymer.

DSC curves presented on figures 2 and 3 showed that the crystallization of each block strongly depends on the copolymers composition and that

increasing the PEG block amount in the copolymer leads to an increase of PEG crystallinity, as shown on figure 1, which corresponds to the DSC curve of copolymer 1 (higher amount of PEG in the copolymer). For this polymer, the crystallinity of the PE block is negligible.

For copolymer 2 (lower content of PEG), the crystallinity of PEG disappears. This effect might be explained by the hindrance of PE chains, avoiding the PEG crystallization. The blocks length and the presence of one another block could then modify the crystalline organization.

The crystallinity degrees of the various polymers are given in Table 2.

	M_w (Aldrich)	PE block	PEG block	X_c PE	X_c PEG
	[g/mol]	wt %	wt %	wt %	wt %
Cop 1	2250	17	83	-	89
Cop 2	575	78	22	85	-
PEG 1	2050	-	100	-	95

Table 2: Crystallinity degree of PE-b-PEG copolymers (Cop 1 and Cop 2) and PEG homopolymer (PEG 1)

Bulk PE-b-PEG copolymers and the corresponding homopolymers (PE and PEG) have been analyzed by Attenuated Total Reflection infrared spectroscopy (ATR), as reference spectra, in order to identify the different absorption peak of each polymer, representative of the bulk organization (polymer pellets are directly analyzed by ATR).

Thin films of PE-b-PEG copolymers deposited on aluminum substrates will then be studied by PM-

IRRAS (reflection mode), in order to investigate the effect of confinement (induced by the thin layer) on the copolymers organization.

ATR spectra of PE, PEG 1 and copolymer 1 are presented on figure 4.

Fig 4. ATR spectra of bulk PE, PEG (PEG1) and PE-b-PEG (Cop 1)

Five main regions are present for PE-b-PEG copolymers :

- The OH region (3000-3500 cm^{-1})
- The CH_2 stretching mode region (2600-3000 cm^{-1})
- The CH_2 angular deformation mode region (1200-1500 cm^{-1})
- The COC stretching mode region (1000-1200 cm^{-1})
- The CH_2 angular deformation mode region (500-1000 cm^{-1})

The C-O-C stretching mode region, characteristic of PEG blocks will be analyzed in details. Peaks attribution in the ATR spectra have been assigned thanks to the reference of Yoshihara [4] for the PEG bands.

Thin films of PE-b-PEG copolymers (deposited on aluminum substrates) have been studied by PM-IRRAS. Comparison of ATR and PM-IRRAS spectra for Copolymer 1 is presented in figure 5. The objective is to identify some modification in peaks intensity or position due to the effect of confinement.

Fig 5. ATR spectrum (top) of bulk PE-b-PEG (Cop 1) compared with PM-IRRAS spectrum (bottom) of thin film adsorbed on aluminum substrate

Some peaks intensities and positions are different on PM-IRRAS and ATR spectra.

The CH_2 peak of PE block at 2848 cm^{-1} is highly reduced. The C-O-C peak at 1279 cm^{-1} and the CH_2 rocking at 1359 cm^{-1} of PEG also disappear on PM-IRRAS spectrum as shown more in details on figure 6. These differences evidenced some changes in chains organization and morphology when the copolymer is adsorbed in thin layer on a polar substrate like aluminium.

Fig 6. ATR spectrum of bulk PE-b-PEG (Cop 1) compared with PM-IRRAS spectrum of thin film adsorbed on aluminum substrate in the region 1000-1400 cm^{-1}

At 1100cm^{-1} the C-O-C peak of PEG is highly shifted to the higher frequencies and both peaks surrounding at 1146 cm^{-1} and 1060 cm^{-1} also disappear. According to a recent study [2], this single peak emerging at 1120 cm^{-1} is due to an amorphization of the PEG phase.

For example, the bulk crystallinity for PEG block was equal to 89 % and seems to be strongly reduced in thin films. Interactions between PEG groups and polar aluminum surface could explain this decrease of crystallinity.

The influence of the diblocks composition and chains length on thin films organization will be discussed in terms of molecular orientations that can be probed by PM-IRRAS specific selection rules.

Spectra analysis combined with the examination of all transition dipole moment directions allow us to observe the extinction of all parallel transition dipole moments.

Bands at 1146 cm^{-1} and 1060 cm^{-1} disappear because they are combination bands for which the asymmetric stretching C-O-C is predominant and parallel to the main chain axis. The extinction of the asymmetric stretching C-O-C is a consequence of the parallel orientation of the PEG chain axis relative to the metal surface. Moreover, oxygen

atoms tend to be oriented facing the polar surface of aluminum, which is relevant with the fact that the PEG chains are flattened on the surface.

The influence of the copolymer composition on thin films organization can also be discussed.

Figure 7 compares the PM-IRRAS spectra of both copolymers (Cop 1 and Cop 2) in the $2700\text{-}3100\text{cm}^{-1}$ region. Copolymer 1 contains 83 % of PEG and copolymer 2 contains 22% of PEG.

Fig. 7 : PM-IRRAS spectra of PE-b-PEG copolymer 1 (83 wt % of PEG) compared with PM-IRRAS spectra of PE-b-PEG copolymer 2 (22 wt % of PEG) deposited on aluminum substrate in the 2700 and 3100 cm^{-1} region

PM-IRRAS spectrum of copolymer 2 (lower content of PEG) indicates that the vibration mode corresponding to the symmetric stretching mode of CH_2 of PEG (at 2860 cm^{-1} , corresponding to peak “a” for copolymer 1) is off.

Elsewhere, for copolymer 2, the vibration mode corresponding to the symmetric stretching mode of CH_2 of PE (at 2846 cm^{-1} , corresponding to peak “e” for copolymer 2) appears.

The asymmetric stretching mode of CH₂ peak of PE (at 2914 cm⁻¹, corresponding to peak “g” for copolymer 2) is also intensified, in correlation with the a higher amount of PE in copolymer 2. These peaks modifications indicate changes in the conformation of the chains on the aluminum surface, depending on the chemical composition of the copolymers.

The effect of the aluminium surface, and the confinement of the copolymers (thin films) are then able to induce some changes in polymers morphology.

Morphology of polymers films have been studied by optical microscopy. Polymers films (deposited on a glass plate) have been heated at 120°C and then cooled. The cooling, inducing crystallization, has been followed by optical microscopy
Figure 8 presents the morphology of PEG film (PEG1).

Fig. 8 : Optical microscopy image of PEG film (PEG1)

The presence of large spherulites can be observed on figure 8, in accordance with the high crystallinity of PEG 1 (crystallinity degree = 95%).

PE-b-PEG copolymers have been also studied by optical microscopy (thin films deposited on glass).
Figure 9 shows below the optical microscopy image obtained after the cooling of copolymer 1.

Fig. 9 : Optical microscopy image of PE-b-PEG (Cop 1) film

For copolymer 1 (which contains 83% of PEG), PEG crystals are visible, but are smaller than the large spherulites observed for PEG homopolymer. This can be explained by the shorter PEG blocks and by the hindrance of PE blocks.

Figure 10 shows below the optical microscopy image of Cop 2.

Fig. 10 : Optical microscopy image of PE-b-PEG (Cop 2) film

For copolymer 2 (which contains 22% of PEG), PE crystals are mainly visible (crystallization at a

temperature closed to the PE crystallization temperature).

AFM imaging of thin films surface allows us to confirm the copolymer organization investigated previously by PM-IRRAS. PM-IRRAS results have indeed shown some changes in shape and width of C-O-C absorption bands (around 1100 cm^{-1}) corresponding to a possible amorphization. This hypothesis has been confirmed by atomic force microscopy on the homopolymer PEG 1, as illustrated on figure 11, which presents the surface of PEG1 before and after annealing.

Fig. 11. AFM (tapping mode) amplitude images of PEG 1 (a) before annealing, scan area $10 \times 10\ \mu\text{m}$, (b) after annealing scan area $10 \times 10\ \mu\text{m}$

The image obtained before annealing is representative of the thin film deposited on aluminium (by spin coating).

For AFM analysis, polymers have been spin coated on silicon wafer, in order to have a very smooth surface. However, silicon wafer is a polar substrate like aluminium.

An important difference of structure can be seen on Figure 11 before and after annealing.

Before annealing (Figure 11.a) the polymer tends to form multi-layers but no well defined organization can be seen.

After annealing over the melting temperature and cooled the polymer has crystallized as shown by the multi-layers of lamellas structure.

The amorphization of the polymer after adsorption on a polar substrate (before annealing) observed by

PM-IRRAS on PEG homopolymer and Cop 1 (large amount of PEG) is then confirmed by atomic force microscopy analysis.

4 Conclusion

PE-b-PEG diblock copolymers and their organization on an aluminum substrate have been investigated by PM-IRRAS spectroscopy. This technique allowed us to characterize the chains orientation and conformation in order to understand the competition between chains/chains and chains/substrate interactions, which will have a direct effect on the blocks cristallinity.

PM-IRRAS appears to be an adequate tool to access the chain organization in thin films.

Further experiences will be also performed with the same diblock copolymers, deposited as thin films onto model substrates (silicon wafer or gold) chemically grafted (by silanes or thiols molecules), in order to better understand the role of the substrate surface chemistry (hydrophilic or hydrophobic substrate) on polymer chains organization.

The investigation of this chains organization would allow us to better understand what can happen at a fiber/polymer interface in composite materials.

Acknowledgments

The author would like to thank the University of Haute Alsace (UHA) for financial support.

References

- [1] T. Elzein, V. Kreim, S. Bistac, "Confinement of polystyrene at interfaces : Consequences on chain orientation", *Journal of Polymer Science. Part B. Polymer physics A.*, vol 44, pp 1268-1276, 2006.
- [2] T.Elzein, H.Awada, M.Nasser-Eddine, C.Delaite, M.Brogly, "A model of chain folding in Polycaprolactone-b-Polymethyl Methacrylate diblock copolymers", *Thin Solid Films* vol 483, pp 388-395, 2005.
- [3] T.Elzein, M.Brogly, J.Schultz, "Quantitative calculation of the orientation angles of adsorbed polyamides nanofilms", *Polymer* Vol 44, pp 3649-3660, 2003.

- [4] T. Yoshihara, H. Tadokoro, S. Murahashi, "Normal vibrations of the polymer molecules of helical conformation. IV. Polyethylene oxide and polyethylene-d₄ oxide", *J.Chem.Phys*, vol 41, pp 2902-2911, 1964.